

**RUSSIAN BORROWWORDS IN L. ULITSKAYA'S "THE
LADY WITH THE DOG"****Jayron Jumaniozova Ulugbek kizi**
Kashkadarya Region, KarshiInternational Innovation University
First-year Master's student.**Laylo Normuradovna Elmuradova**

jayroniskandarova@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18496700>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 03rd February 2026Accepted: 04th February 2026Online: 05th February 2026**KEYWORDS***borrowed words, foreign language vocabulary, modern Russian language, literary text, L. Ulitskaya, stylistic function, vocabulary, literary analysis***ABSTRACT**

This article analyzes Russian borrowings from L. Ulitskaya's "The Lady with the Dog." The topic is relevant given the active process of lexical borrowing in modern speech and its artistic interpretation in literature. The aim of the study is to identify the functional features and stylistic role of foreign vocabulary in the text, as well as to determine how borrowings help the author create the social, cultural, and psychological context of the narrative. The study examines the main thematic groups of borrowed words found in the work, their origins, and the degree of their adaptation to the Russian language. Particular attention is paid to how foreign language elements reflect cultural realities, urban environments, the speech characteristics of the characters, and their social affiliation.

Language is a living system in constant motion. As a result of the development of society, the expansion of intercultural contacts, the development of science and technology, the vocabulary of each language is updated and enriched. In this process, especially loanwords play an important role. Loanwords are considered valuable not only as a means of expressing new concepts, but also as a linguistic phenomenon reflecting the socio-cultural landscape of a particular era. Therefore, the study of loanwords in literary texts is of particular importance in modern linguistics.

The Russian language has also historically been in active contact with various languages, and as a result, many words from French, German, English, Latin, Greek and other sources have taken a strong place in its vocabulary. Especially in the literature of the 19th and 20th centuries, loanwords were used as an important stylistic tool to express the speech of a certain social stratum, describe the environment, and reveal the worldview of characters. In modern literature, this process has become even more active, and the borrowed vocabulary has become an artistic expression of global cultural influences.

This article is devoted to the analysis of the features of the use of borrowed words on the example of the work of the Russian writer Lyudmila Ulitskaya "The Lady with a Dog". Ulitskaya's work is distinguished in modern Russian literature by its unique style, subtle psychologism and attention to the details of everyday life. In her works, language means, in

particular borrowed words, play an important artistic role in revealing the inner world, social background and cultural environment of the characters.

The relevance of the study is that by determining the function of borrowed vocabulary in a literary text, it is possible to understand not only the processes of language development, but also how modern human thinking and cultural identification are expressed through language. Borrowed words often become not just a means of naming, but also a semantic and stylistic sign indicating the social status, level of education, professional activity or worldview of the character.

The purpose of the article is to identify the borrowed words in the work, indicate their sources of origin, and highlight their stylistic and artistic functions in the text. At the same time, the role of borrowed vocabulary in the speech of the characters, their interaction with the author's speech, and their importance in creating a general artistic atmosphere are also analyzed.

Every word used in a work of art is not accidental. In particular, borrowed words are consciously chosen by the author and carry a certain social, cultural, or psychological meaning in the text. In L. Ulitskaya's work "Lady with a Dog", borrowed vocabulary is not just a sign of modernity, but also an important stylistic tool that reveals the living environment, worldview, and inner state of the characters.

For example, words such as "cafe", "restaurant", "menu", "office" found in the description of everyday life came from French and English, and they express a lifestyle characteristic of urban culture. If the author had used purely Russian alternatives such as "kitchen" or "workshop", the image would have been far removed from the modern urban environment. Thus, borrowed words serve the function of linking reality to a specific era and place.

In Ulitskaya's works, the speech of the characters is one of the main tools for showing their social status and cultural level. Borrowed words enhance this speech characteristic.

For example, in the speech of representatives of the intelligentsia, words of Greek and Latin origin such as "intellectual", "philosophy", "culture", "analysis" are actively used. These lexical units indicate that the character has a rich spiritual world, is a bookish, thinking person. In the speech of a character from a simpler social class, such terminological or bookish borrowings are less common.[3]

Also, words of English origin, such as "business", "contract", "project", "image", reflecting the modern lifestyle, provide additional information about the professional activities or life views of the characters. For example, the word "image" in the sentence "he thought a lot about his image" indicates that the character pays great attention to his appearance and social impression.

The borrowed vocabulary is actively involved not only in the character's speech, but also in the author's description. Such words used by the author often serve to realistically depict the environment, give the spirit of the times, or create a slightly ironic tone.

For example, the use of words such as "interior", "design", "style", "detail" in the description of the interior indicates that the space is modern and tastefully decorated. If words such as "furnishing" or "decoration" were used, the description would be a little more general and less expressive. Therefore, colloquialisms enhance the clarity of the image.

Sometimes the author also uses colloquialisms to express light sarcasm towards the character. For example, a character who considers himself very "progressive" may use a foreign language in his speech. Excessive use of words introduced later may indicate that he is an artificial or self-serving person.

The borrowed vocabulary found in the work can be conditionally divided into several thematic groups:

a) Culture and art

Words such as "theater", "museum", "concert", "artist", "role" serve to describe the cultural environment in the work. Through them, the aesthetic tastes and cultural interests of the characters are revealed.

b) Domestic and urban life

Words such as "metro", "bus", "route", "supermarket" represent the urban space. This vocabulary connects the work with specific city life.

c) Psychological and abstract concepts

Words such as "stress", "depression", "emotion", "instinct" allow the characters' inner experiences to be expressed in more precise and modern terms.[2]

The borrowed vocabulary also gives the text its own rhythm and tone. The phonetic structure of words from foreign languages often differs from Russian words, and this also adds variety to the sound system of the text. In particular, short and sonorous English words give the text dynamism.

In addition, borrowed words create the effect of modernity. Through such vocabulary, the reader feels that the events relate to the present or the recent past. This enhances the realistic effect of the work.

In Ulitskaya's text, borrowed words are often used in accordance with the grammatical system of the Russian language: they receive Russian suffixes, are subject to gender and case categories. For example, such forms as "projects", "in the office", "designer" indicate the process of language assimilation.[5]

This means that borrowed words are not an alien element, but are an active part of the language. In a literary text, such adaptation enhances the effect of natural speech.

Thus, in the work "The Lady with the Dog", borrowed words serve as an important artistic tool for describing the social environment, revealing the character of the hero, giving the spirit of the times and introducing stylistic diversity to the text. Through them, the author not only describes reality, but also takes the reader into a certain cultural and spiritual space.

In conclusion, borrowed words in the work "The Lady with the Dog" occupy an important place in the content and stylistic structure of the literary text. Through them, the author creates a picture of modern life, deepens the character of the heroes and enhances the overall aesthetic effect of the work. Therefore, the study of borrowed vocabulary is of great scientific importance not only in understanding the development of the language, but also in understanding the features of artistic thinking.

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